

ESTIMATING INTERLAMINAR STRESS DISTRIBUTIONS AROUND HOLES

IN COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

A simple, approximate technique to predict the sign and relative magnitude of interlaminar normal stresses around a hole in a laminate is presented. The method assumes that the only ply stresses that contribute to the interlaminar effect are those radial stresses induced by the lamination of dissimilar plies, near the hole boundary. These stresses are then used in a free-body analysis of the free-edge to determine the out-of-plane stresses. The results are compared with numerical results from the literature. The method shows fair agreement for a wide range of laminates. Results may be in error significantly at interfaces where the numerical results indicate both a singularity and a sudden change in sign at the free-edge.

Introduction

This paper describes a simple technique to predict the sign and relative magnitude of interlaminar stresses around a hole in a laminate, as part of a larger experimental program studying the behaviour of notched laminates. As such, the aim was to reduce the hole problem to an equivalent 2-D problem, and to use simple solutions such as Pagano and Pipes^[1]. The line of approach was partly inspired by observations in the literature, as noted in the review by Salamon^[2], that the sign of the interlaminar normal stress around a hole is not open to intuitive equilibrium arguments.

We will show, by use of examples, that it appears that the hole problem may be approximated by a 2-D formulation, and that simple equilibrium arguments may be used, wherever their use would be allowed in an equivalent straight free-edge problem. It will be shown by reference to the literature that where numerical solutions show singularities, simple arguments can be equally inadequate in both the hole and free-edge problems.

There are very few numerical solutions for the hole problem in the literature, especially when compared to the large number of solutions for the straight edge problem. We will compare our results with those of Raju and Crews^[3] and Rybicki and Schmueser^[4]. The results of Raju and Crews are especially of interest, in that along with their 3-D solution they present a reduced 2-D numerical solution which is the numerical method equivalent to our approach.

Method of Analysis

We approximate the laminate at the circular edge of the hole by a series of straight edge laminates, whose principal directions coincide with the radial and tangential directions (Fig. 1). Each of these straight edge laminates is subjected to a set of non-uniform laminate stresses, as calculated from the exact plane stress solution^[5,6].

Raju and Crews^[3] have shown that the exact analytical solution may be used to describe accurately the laminate stress field, right up to the hole boundary. The requirement that the radial and shear laminate stresses decay to zero at the hole boundary is satisfied.

The reasoning for the existence of interlaminar stresses around a hole can be seen as analogous to the reasoning for their existence in the straight edge case. In the straight edge problem, it is the transverse stresses generated by the applied axial load on the laminate that give rise to the interlaminar effects (Fig. 2). If we superpose additional transverse loads on the laminates, they will not affect the interlaminar stresses, as these loads are balanced by additional transverse ply stresses at the edge. In the same vein, it is not the radial and shear stresses calculated by the exact plane stress solution that give rise to interlaminar stresses, but it is the additional ply radial stresses due to lamination that do so. Away from the hole, the sum of these stresses through the thickness is zero, and there is no perturbation from the exact plane stress solution. At the hole boundary, however, these ply radial stresses must have decayed to zero from the values predicted by the combined laminated plate theory (LPT) and exact plane stress solution. The out-of-plane stresses will have increased to maintain force and moment equilibrium. In this manner, we can reduce the problem to the familiar Pagano and Pipes^[1] form, and use their approximate solution to predict

Fig. 1: Straight edge approximation of a laminate hole.

Fig. 2: Free-body equilibrium diagram, from [10].

the interlaminar normal stress. The radial and tangential directions of the 3-D problem become the transverse and axial directions in the equivalent 2-D laminate.

In the hole problem we have a non-uniform stress field, and we must therefore first simplify the problem further, and decide on some representative value for the radial ply stresses to be used as input to the Pagano and Pipes equation.

Using laminated plate theory (LPT), we calculate the variation of the transverse (or radial) ply stresses as function of distance from the hole edge. To arrive at a value of the transverse stress for input to the Pagano and Pipes solution, we have suggested and used three different approximations:-

- (i) The first option (Fig. 3) is to consider the laminate stresses on a boundary, distance l away from the hole boundary. We assume that beyond this periphery any lamination transverse (radial) ply stresses can exist, as predicted by LPT, but that within this boundary, moving towards the hole, the lamination radial ply stresses must decay, in a manner not predicted by LPT. Thus given the laminate stresses we can calculate the transverse ply stresses as

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_y^k &= (\bar{Q}_{12}^k A_{11}^{-1} + \bar{Q}_{22}^k A_{12}^{-1} + \bar{Q}_{26}^k A_{16}^{-1}) h \sigma_x^L(a+l) \\ &+ (\bar{Q}_{12}^k A_{12}^{-1} + \bar{Q}_{22}^k A_{22}^{-1} + \bar{Q}_{26}^k A_{26}^{-1}) h \sigma_y^L(a+l) \\ &+ (\bar{Q}_{12}^k A_{16}^{-1} + \bar{Q}_{22}^k A_{26}^{-1} + \bar{Q}_{26}^k A_{66}^{-1}) h \tau_{xy}^L(a+l) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

However, a component of this stress, namely the second term of Equation 1, is due to the laminate radial stress, and as this component decays to zero according to the exact plane stress solution, it need not be included. Thus the component of the radial stress that is responsible for the out-of-plane stresses is:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\sigma}_y^k &= (\bar{Q}_{12}^k A_{11}^{-1} + \bar{Q}_{22}^k A_{12}^{-1} + \bar{Q}_{26}^k A_{16}^{-1}) h \sigma_x^L(a+l) \\ &+ (\bar{Q}_{12}^k A_{16}^{-1} + \bar{Q}_{22}^k A_{26}^{-1} + \bar{Q}_{26}^k A_{66}^{-1}) h \tau_{xy}^L(a+l) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

- (ii) The second option (Fig. 4) is to consider that the laminate stresses vary with radial distance. We assume that for the purpose of ensuring equilibrium it is the average value of these stresses that matters, and thus we use the integrated average value of the stresses to calculate the ply radial stresses. Again, we subtract out the radial component due to the exact plane stress solution and are left with

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\sigma}_y^k &= (\bar{Q}_{12}^k A_{11}^{-1} + \bar{Q}_{22}^k A_{12}^{-1} + \bar{Q}_{26}^k A_{16}^{-1}) \frac{h}{l} \int_a^{a+l} \sigma_x^L(y) dy \\ &+ (\bar{Q}_{12}^k A_{16}^{-1} + \bar{Q}_{22}^k A_{26}^{-1} + \bar{Q}_{26}^k A_{66}^{-1}) \frac{h}{l} \int_a^{a+l} \tau_{xy}^L(y) dy \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Fig.3: Stresses used in point stress approximation.

Fig. 4: Stresses used in average and modified average approximation.

(iii) The third option is similar to the second in that we consider the the average integrated stress values. In order to allow for the component of the ply stresses that would decay to zero as part of the exact plane stress solution, we subtract out the laminate radial stress, rather than the lamina radial stress. Though this approach is difficult to explain in terms of physical reasoning (the plies see the same strain, not stress), it appears to give results that match numerical solutions very well. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{\sigma}_y^k = & \left(\bar{Q}_{12}^k A_{11}^{-1} + \bar{Q}_{22}^k A_{12}^{-1} + \bar{Q}_{26}^k A_{16}^{-1} \right) \frac{h}{\lambda} \int_a^{a+\lambda} \sigma_x^L(y) dy \\
 & + \left(\bar{Q}_{12}^k A_{12}^{-1} + \bar{Q}_{22}^k A_{22}^{-1} + \bar{Q}_{26}^k A_{26}^{-1} \right) \frac{h}{\lambda} \int_a^{a+\lambda} \sigma_y^L(y) dy \quad (4) \\
 & + \left(\bar{Q}_{12}^k A_{16}^{-1} + \bar{Q}_{22}^k A_{26}^{-1} + \bar{Q}_{26}^k A_{66}^{-1} \right) \frac{h}{\lambda} \int_a^{a+\lambda} \tau_{xy}^L(y) dy \\
 & - \frac{1}{\lambda} \int_a^{a+\lambda} \sigma_y^L(y) dy
 \end{aligned}$$

Results and Discussion

We consider first a (90/0)s laminate with the elastic properties as used by Raju and Crews (see Table I). Plotted in Figures 5, 6 and 7 are results for the $z=h$ plane for the three different methods described above. For convenience, we will refer to them as the point, average, and modified average approximations from now on.

For each method, we show the effect of assuming different characteristic lengths λ . The effect of varying the transition length is similar in all three cases. With $\lambda = 0$ that is using the stresses on the hole boundary only, all three methods reduce to the same solution, and we are considering only the effect of the laminate circumferential stress^[7]. As we allow the transition length to increase, the increasing laminate shear stress and changing laminate circumferential stress cause the distributions to shift to the left and increase in magnitude. All three methods give essentially similar values except that the modified average approximation predicts a sign change for $\theta \gtrsim 75^\circ$. It is generally assumed that the range over which interlaminar effects occur is one laminate thickness, which corresponds to a value of $\lambda = 0.2a$ for the Raju and Crews geometry. We will use this value of λ/a for all our comparisons.

Plotted in Figure 8 are the results from the numerical analysis, and the $\lambda = 0.2a$ curves from our three different approximations. Agreement is fairly good over most of the quadrant, though both the point and average methods predict the wrong sign for $\theta \gtrsim 80^\circ$. The physically less acceptable modified average method gives better agreement even in this region. It is important to emphasize that the $z=h$ plane is an interface between the 0 and 90 plies, and the Raju and Crews solution indicates a singularity at this interface. Though we cannot cope with the singularity, we appear to predict the same general shape, though with consistently lower magnitudes.

TABLE I: Material Properties Used

Type of Laminate	Elastic Properties of the 0° Lamina
(0/90) _s (90/0) _s Ref. [3]	$E_{11} = 138.0$ GPa $E_{22} = 14.5$ GPa $G_{12} = 5.86$ GPa $\nu_{12} = 0.21$
(0 ₂ /± 30/∓ 30) _s (± 30/∓ 30/0 ₂) _s (± 45/∓ 45/90 ₂) _s (90 ₂ /± 45/∓ 45) _s Ref. [4]	$E_{11} = 151.60$ GPa $E_{22} = 11.00$ GPa $G_{11} = 6.89$ GPa $\nu_{12} = 0.25$

Fig. 5: Effect of l/a on σ_z at $z=h$ in a $(90/0)_s$ laminate, using point stress method.

Fig. 6: Effect of l/a on σ_z at $z=h$ in a $(90/0)_s$ laminate, using average stress method.

Fig. 7: Effect of l/a on σ_z at $z=h$ in a $(90/0)_s$ laminate, using modified average stress method.

Raju and Crews also present results for a $(0/90)_s$ laminate. These results are very similar to their $(90/0)_s$ values, both in magnitude and sign. Our solution for a $(0/90)_s$ would be equal in magnitude to the $(90/0)_s$ solution but opposite in sign. However, close inspection of the results in Raju and Crews shows that in the case of the $(0/90)_s$ laminate not only does the interlaminar normal stress distribution through the thickness of the laminate become singular as it approaches the $z=h$ interface but it also changes sign over a very short distance before the interface. The $(90/0)_s$ laminate does not show this very abrupt reversal, and therefore allows comparison. The $(0/90)_s$ behaviour appears not to be a 3-D effect, but a result of having a very fine mesh in the region of interest. This is shown by the fact that their finite element 2-D results agree closely with their 3-D results, and that their 2-D results are influenced only slightly by whether they include shear stresses in their analysis or not. Thus it appears that it is possible, even in the 2-D case, to have out-of-plane stresses at the free edge different in sign to what an equilibrium argument would suggest. Similar results exist in the free-edge literature. For example results from Wang and Crossman^[8] for a $(90/0)_s$ laminate, and Pagano^[9] for a boron-epoxy/epoxy laminate, show the same sign change behaviour at the $z=h$ interface, but not at the $z=0$ interface, where there is no discontinuity in material properties. Similarly, the Raju and Crews data show that at the $z=0$ interface the $(0/90)_s$ laminate has an interlaminar stress of opposite sign to the $(90/0)_s$ laminate over most of the boundary. However, the mesh is very coarse at the $z=0$ interface, and no detailed results are presented by them. Thus it appears that the problem lies not in reducing the 3-D problem to a 2-D approximation, but in the 2-D equilibrium argument. However, there is a great deal of experimental evidence to back the equilibrium argument in the 2-D case, and a great deal of use is made of it.

Figures 9 and 10 show the results for the $(0_2/\pm 30/\mp 30)_s$ laminate analysed by Rybicki and Schmueser. The elastic properties are listed in Table I. All results are for the laminate mid-plane where there is no discontinuity in material properties, and thus no singularity is expected. As a fairly coarse mesh was used by Rybicki and Schmueser, there is no indication of any such effects. Figure 9 shows that the main effect of increasing the transition length is to decrease the value of the normal stress for small θ . The change in sign at about $\theta = 75^\circ$ remains unchanged. For comparison with the numerical data in Figure 10, we have plotted our solutions for all three approximations, again using a transition length equal to the laminate thickness. Agreement is reasonable with all three approximate methods correctly predicting a sign change for $\theta > 60^\circ$. The modified average approximation shows the best agreement. We consistently predict larger magnitudes than the numerical results. Rybicki and Schmueser also present the distribution for a $(\pm 30/\mp 30/0_2)_s$ lay-up, and though the sign of the distribution is reversed, it is not an exact mirror image as predicted by our method. They predict magnitudes for the $(\pm 30/\mp 30/0_2)_s$ laminate that are roughly double those of the $(0_2/\pm 30/\mp 30)_s$ lay-up.

Figure 11 shows the results for a $(\pm 45/\mp 45/90_2)_s$ laminate. We observe good agreement in sign and relative magnitude. We would predict a mirror image for a $(90_2/\pm 45/\mp 45)_s$ laminate, whereas Rybicki and Schmueser report a distribution, which though of opposite sign, shows much less variation in magnitude as function of angle.

Fig. 8: Present results ($l/a = 0.2$) compared with numerical solution for $(90/0)_s$ laminate at $z=h$.

Fig. 9: Effect of l/a on σ_z at $z=0$ in a $(0_2/\pm 30/\mp 30)_s$ laminate using point stress method.

Fig. 10: Present results ($l/a = 1.2$) compared with numerical solution for a $(0_2/+30/-30)_s$ laminate at $z=0$.

Fig. 11: Present results ($l/a = 1.2$) compared with numerical solution for a $(+45/-45/90_2)_s$ laminate at $z=0$.

In all three lay-ups presented here, and all other lay-ups reported by Rybicki and Schmueser, we have observed that the simple equilibrium argument has some success in predicting the shape and sign of the interlaminar normal stress distribution, contrary to the objection, as reported by Salamon, that equilibrium arguments cannot be used. Furthermore, the picture is even more complicated in practice, as delamination is rarely observed without matrix cracking, which must influence the behaviour considerably. We are now engaged in an experimental program to provide data for comparison.

Conclusions

The simple technique proposed appears to allow the reduction of the 3-D problem to an approximate 2-D problem, and is capable of predicting interlaminar normal stress distributions which are in rough agreement with numerical results in the literature for a wide range of laminates. The results at interfaces with discontinuities may be grossly inaccurate, but not significantly more so than the approximate equilibrium solution for an equivalent straight free-edge problem.

Nomenclature

- x = tangential (longitudinal) direction
- y = radial (transverse) direction
- z = normal direction
- h = ply thickness
- ℓ = radial distance from hole boundary
- a = radius of hole
- θ = angle measured clockwise from loading axis
- σ_z = interlaminar normal stress at hole boundary
- σ_g = gross applied stress
- σ_y^k = radial stress in k^{th} ply
- $\tilde{\sigma}_y^k$ = component of radial stress in k^{th} ply used in calculation of out-of-plane stresses
- $\sigma_x^L(y)$ = laminate tangential stress
- $\sigma_y^L(y)$ = laminate radial stress
- $\tau_{xy}^L(y)$ = laminate shear stress
- $[\bar{Q}_{ij}]^k$ = reduced stiffness matrix of k^{th} ply
- $[A_{ij}]^{-1}$ = inverse extensional stiffness matrix of equivalent straight-edge laminate

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References

1. N.J. Pagano and R.B. Pipes, "Some Observations on the Interlaminar Strength of Composite Laminates," Int. J. Mechanical Sciences, V.15, (1973), pp. 679-688.
2. N.J. Salamon, "An Assessment of the Interlaminar Stress Problem in Laminated Composites," J. Composite Materials Supplement, V. 14, (1980) pp. 177-194.
3. I.S. Raju and J.H. Crews, Jr., "Three-Dimensional Analysis of (0/90)s and (90/0)s Laminates with a Central Circular Hole," Composites Technology Review, V. 4, No. 4, (1982), pp. 116-124.
4. E.F. Rybicki and D.W. Schmueser, "Effect of Stacking Sequence and Lay-up Angle on Free-Edge Stresses around a Hole in a Laminated Plate under Tension", J. Composite Materials,", V. 12 (1978), pp. 300-313.
5. S.G. Lekhnitskii, Theory of Elasticity of Anisotropic Elastic Body, Holden-Day Inc., Inc., 1963.
6. G.N. Savin, Stress Distribution around Holes, Translation of "Raspredeleniye Napryazheniy Okolo Otvorstiy," "Navkova Dunka" Press, Kiev, 1968, National Aeronautics and Space Administration Technical Translation NASA TT F-607.
7. T.K. O'Brien and I.S. Raju, "Strain-Energy-Release Rate Analysis of Delamination Around an Open Hole in Composite Laminates," AIAA-84-0961, pp. 526- 536, Presented at 25th Structures, Structural Dynamics and Materials Conference, Palm Springs, California, May, 1984.
8. A.S.D. Wang and F.W. Crossman, "Some New Results on Edge Effect in Symmetric Composite Laminates", J. Composite Materials, V.11 (1977), pp. 92-106.
9. N.J. Pagano, "Stress Fields in Composite Laminates," Int. J. Solids Structures, V.14, (1978) pp. 385-400.
10. J.M. Whitney and C.E. Browning, "Free-Edge Delamination of Tensile Coupons," J. Composite Materials, V.6 (1972), pp. 300-303.

